

MODERN VIEW ON THE ETIOLOGY, PATHOGENESIS AND TREATMENT METHODS FOR COXOARTHROSIS

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Annotation. Considering the evolution of human development, it is impossible not to notice that nature has laid down two extremely important phenomena of harmonious self-organization-proportion and symmetry-in the structure of the musculoskeletal system. This is nothing more than an expression of the law of balanced proportionality and consistency of human body parts united into a single whole. The main connecting and coordinating elements in this single system of harmony of the form and function of the UDF are numerous joints.. In Uzbekistan, ODS diseases account for more than one - third of all outpatient requests for medical care to doctors of various specialties, and this is despite the fact that 70% of those who are ill are treated independently and only 30% reach the doctor [7, 9]. In the first place in the structure of these diseases are degenerative-dystrophic and dysplastic diseases of large joints and spine.

Keywords: coxarthrosis, treatment, diagnosis

According to various sources, they make up 48-67. 5% of the total acute pathology in working-age and especially elderly people [2, 3]. For many years, scientists and practitioners around the world believed that dystrophic joint lesions are the lot of the elderly and that due to the aging process, they are irreversible [1, 2]. Noting the fallacy of such a judgment, V. M. Dilman (1987) writes: "It would be wrong to assume that at a certain age the time for treatment is lost: aging is a physiological phenomenon and it is a disease of disturbed regulation, so in many respects it can be treated" [2]. The same idea is expressed by D. E. Drexler in his research on the mechanisms of aging of a living cell [6]. Diseases called "aging" are natural, the author believes, just as "smallpox" was natural, but it was defeated by the efforts and desire of scientists. The prospect of the victory of science, if not over old age, then over the diseases of aging, he reveals in his theory of the restoration of aging cells, suggesting to use "nanomachines", or "repair machines", on the principle of molecular "recognition". Bob Arnot, one of the recognized modern foreign experts in the field of medicine and health, came to the conclusion that the process of dystrophic disorders in the joints is manageable [2]. Based on numerous scientific studies of scientists from the USA and Great Britain, as well as extensive personal experience, he developed a program for the treatment of dystrophic joint diseases at the earliest stages of their manifestation, created a concept for the prevention and management of pathological processes regardless of the patient's age. Today, these works are gaining special social significance, as numerous studies in recent years have established a rapid increase in dystrophic and dysplastic diseases of DDS in young people (up to 40 years), as well as in children and adolescents [2]. According to Y. Y. Popelyansky [7], osteochondrosis and arthrosis begin to develop in almost every person in 20-25 years, although their clinical manifestations, due to the chronic but progressive course of the disease, are detected much later and, consequently, are diagnosed late. The peculiarity of these diseases is that they are protracted in nature. Coxarthrosis consistently ranks second after gonarthrosis in the overall structure of joint pathology in terms of incidence and first in terms of temporary and

persistent disability [7, 10, 11,]. The share of disabled people due to coxarthrosis of various origins is from 20 to 30% of those disabled due to joint diseases [2,]. According to international statistics, the number of patients with coxarthrosis varies among the world's population from 10 % to 12 % of all ODD diseases[15]. According to ICD-10 (Geneva, 1995), coxarthrosis belongs to the group of "Osteoarthritis" (OA). It is worth noting that neither in foreign nor in domestic literature there is a clear distinction in the definition of the concepts: "deforming osteoarthritis "(DA),"osteoarthritis"(OA),"metabolic dystrophic osteoarthritis "(OA),"arthroarthritis"(AA),"osteoarthritis". Most foreign authors regard this pathological process as "osteoarthritis" and " arthroarthritis" of the hip joint [4] In the Russian literature, the definitions "deforming osteoarthritis and metabolic -dystrophic osteoarthritis "are more often used" [5]. The above-mentioned B. Arnot [2] uses the term "joint wear". Osteoarthritis, in his opinion, is a mechanical destruction of the joint caused by its wear (wear). Arthritis is the culmination of prolonged wear and tear of the joint elements, when mechanical damage "triggers chemical reactions" leading to destruction and transformation of the joint, and when metabolic disorders are accompanied by inflammatory phenomena. The general formula that defines the essence of any) osteoarthritis(s) is reduced, according to most researchers, to the fact that this is a systemic polyethological joint disease characterized by a progressive chronic course, impaired function, more or less pronounced pain, deformity of the anatomical structures of the joints and morphological changes in their tissue components, loss of temporary and persistent работоса sharp decline in the quality of life, high disability of patients, lack of effective means and methods of treatment and rehabilitation, thereby determining the problem of both medical and social significance. [11, 12]. All this applies equally to coxarthrosis. The widespread public concern about this problem also lies in the fact that, despite the well-known achievements in biology, medicine, genetics and pharmacology in recent years, the incidence of osteoarthritis and coxarthrosis, in particular, is notdecreasing. Moreover, the forecast for 2022 G. promises to double the number of cases of OA in different age groups, especially in people over 50 years of age [4,]. All this served as a basis for considering ODD diseases at the level of WHO, which declared 2000-2010. The "International Decade of Bone and Joint Diseases" and a period of purposeful search for not only means and methods of treatment, but also prevention of these diseases [7]. The primary role in solving both problems is given to a deep systematic study of the causes and mechanisms of the development of the disease, because the effectiveness of treatment can only be counted on if it is pathogenetically justified. Current views on the etiology and pathogenesis of coxarthrosis. Medicine knows more than 23,600 different causal human diseases [4]. Most of them are polyethological. According to many researchers, coxarthrosis also belongs to this groupкоккартроз. At the same time, a number of factors are identified that determine its nosological characteristics, features of clinical and functional manifestations and course (post-traumatic, infectious, dystrophic, involutinal, etc., types of joint lesions) [7, 10,]. Among the triggers for the development of the disease, some authors see excessive overloading of the upper pole of the femoral head (so-called non-physiological loads), which by themselves or along with other causes, lead to severe ischemic and dystrophic lesions of structural articular elements and a general violation of the biomechanics of ODS [2]. Others consider bacterial and tissue-specific sensitization of the body to antigens

of supporting tissues to be the main cause [5]. Still others believe that a significant role in the development of coxarthrosis is played by stressful and unfavorable environmental factors, not excluding other causes.[2]. Based on the results of long-term morphological studies of ODS by I. S. Bachu, G. I. Lavrishchev, and G. A. Onoprienko [6], it is proved that the basis and essence of the pathogenesis is primarily ischemic disorders of articular elements, which in all cases inevitably lead to the destruction of bone, cartilage, and soft tissue structures of the joint and, at the same time, to the development of activation of compensatory-adaptive reactions aimed at reconstruction of destroyed articular elements. A number of other authors also point out the leading role of ischemic disorders in the development of osteoarthritis [10, 11,], linking the phases and stages of disease development with these disorders [10, 11,]. However, no matter how diverse the causes may be, they most often fit into the four main causal models proposed by V. M. Dilman (1986, 1987) [21, 22], which can be represented as: extreme external influences, including environmental ones; internal causal factors - genetically mediated developmental anomalies (dysplasia); organizational factors systemic diseases (diseases of the main physiological systems) rheumatism, collagenosis, gout, metabolic disorders, allergies, etc. factors in which coxarthrosis is only a symptom complex of a systemic disease; involutive processes that are considered as physiological metabolic dystrophic, sluggish current diseases, often accompanied by chronic infections [2]. However, even these four models do not fully reveal the mechanism of OA development and do not give any definite answer to the following questions:: how to treat them effectively and what is the basis of prevention? There is a paradoxical situation when, at the level of modern achievements in medicine, biology, bioengineering, genetics and complex bioenergetic and information systems of humans, the main representative of which is UDS, the issues of treating diseases of this system are not always effective and are least studied. Being under the guise of "diseases of old age", metabolic and dystrophic diseases of the joints attracted little attention of researchers, although they begin long before old age. Timely identification of "breakage" in the structural elements of any joint means solving the problem of treatment and prevention of the disease. Therefore, in recent years, the problem of coxarthrosis has increasingly been considered from the perspective of the systemic organization of ODS and the state of musculoskeletal homeostasis [1] taking into account the role of the nervous, hormonal, immune and other functional systems in the development of specific reactions of individual structural elements of the joint (subchondral bone, cartilage synovial membrane, synovial fluid) and soft tissues surrounding the joint, as elements of a single ODS [1, 8,]. A fundamentally new worldview on the problem of the pathogenesis of ODS diseases is revealed by the fundamental research of A. A. Alekseev and co-authors [1] on the role of connective tissue in the structural organization of this system, the main elements of which, by 85-100%, are considered to be the most important % are represented by connective tissue. Based on the foundations of the de-terminant theory of pathology [4], the structural foundations of adaptation and compensation of functional systems [5], as well as the theory of energy-informational exchange at the level of "Human external environment" [6], connective tissue is considered as the main energy-exchange "springboard" and the most powerful bioenergetic control panel for all internal and external energy-informational processes metabolism in the body. In any case of maladaptation of the body's defenses, connective tissue, according to

researchers, primarily provides one of the most important degrees of ODS protection-the preservation -of musculoskeletal homeostasis [1]. The essence of this phenomenon lies in the fact that in the process of human evolutionary development, "nature is always "guided" by the laws: "golden mean", "golden ratio", "symmetry". According to the objectively existing laws of "triunity and trinachalia" [4, 2], it also created the main middle element of life support in the embryo of all living beings in general and of man in particular, the mesoderm. In the process of evolutionary development, it is transformed into the mesenchyme and then into connective tissue, from which all its morphological representations are formed: solid bone, cartilage; liquid-CSF, blood, interstitial fluid; gel-like intercellular, intervertebral and other gels and liquid crystal cell membranes. "The miracle of perfection of any living organism is the cell membrane," he believes. V. M. Dilman, and it is wrong to think that it simply delimits and protects the internal structure of the cell, passively ensuring the flow of necessary substances into it and the release of" waste". It is obvious that its purpose is to differentiate information signals and receive or not pass them into the cell structure" [2]. Indeed, if we imagine that cell membranes simply delimit the membranes, then a signal, for example, to increase the activity of liver, kidney, or other organs, including joints, would be transmitted without obstacles to all cells of the body without exception, thereby creating "chaos" in their vital activity [70]. However, the membrane of each cell is designed so that it receives only the signals it needs, providing the very first level of regulation and protection of all body systems, the level from which complex and highly organized hypothalamic - pituitary systems and endocrine enzyme and hormonal systems controlled by them are activated, which are also not devoid of connective tissue in their structure [1].

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